

ASSESSMENT ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FACEBOOK AS A MARKETING PLATFORM IN ABUYOG, LEYTE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to assess the effectiveness of Facebook as a Marketing Platform for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in Abuyog, Leyte. Due to the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic, business operations were greatly much affected. Thus, the researchers observed that this is indeed a great problem for the business sector. Through observing the current trend of doing business these days with the use of social media, particularly Facebook, the researchers observed that there were MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte which utilized Facebook Marketing Platform. Hence, the researchers would want to assess its effectiveness. The research method employed for this study was quantitative approach and it used Pearson-r correlation to determine the correlation of the variables under study. The research findings showed that the p-value was less than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, “***there was a significant relationship between the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and extent of satisfaction to the extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform.***” This study concludes with practical recommendations from the researchers that all MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte must adapt Facebook marketing in order to boost sales/income as this platform is effective.

Keywords: *effectiveness, satisfaction, Facebook, marketing, MSMEs*

INTRODUCTION

Over the last 40 years, we have seen a significant change in how business is conducted and how people interact with one another. Through the emergence of modern technology, the adoption of social media technology is speeding up, and we can anticipate that it will have a similar impact on businesses now and in the future.

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises or better known by the acronym “MSMEs” are the business entities that are operating here in the Philippines. These MSMEs are relatively smaller compared to huge companies and corporations. Section 3 of Republic Act No. 6977 “The Magna Carta for Small Enterprises” define MSMEs based on the following categories. Micro enterprises are business entities having less than fifty thousand pesos (P50,000) as the starting capital with 5 or less workers. Cottage enterprises are business entities having fifty thousand one to five hundred thousand pesos (P50,001 to P500,000) as the starting capital with 6 to 9 workers. On the other hand, small enterprises are entities that has a starting capital of five hundred thousand one to five million pesos (P500,001 to P5,000,000) with 10 to 99 workers. Lastly, medium scale enterprises are entities having a capital of five million one to twenty million pesos (P5,000,001 to P20,000,000). Here in the Philippines, there are lots of MSMEs since most businesses found in the local setting are small ones. Based on personal observation, this is for a fact in the local setting of Abuyog, Leyte because majority of the enterprises in the town fall under the micro enterprise category. These enterprises started with a capital of less than fifty thousand pesos (P50,000) and majority of these micro enterprises are on the food industry. When the COVID-19 pandemic struck, these small businesses were the hardest hit. These micro businesses suffered a significant loss of income as a result of lockdowns and stay-at-home protocols. Indeed, this is a significant problem for MSMEs, particularly micro businesses, and the task at hand is to find a solution that will allow these businesses to continue to earn despite the pandemic.

With the emergence of technology, new form of communication existed. Communication is no longer limited to personal interactions but there are now platforms that can be used in communicating with people who are far away from us, and one of those platforms is social media. Social media are new forms of communication that changes people's behavior and expectations, as well as how businesses operate. Because of the emergence of social media, users can now use social media platforms to invite and converse with others in an easy-to-use manner. This type of interaction has given millions of customers a voice, allowing them to communicate with one another and share their experiences and opinions. This is indeed true these days. As we can observe, social media users can now post their comments and feedbacks on social media pages, this give users the freedom to also communicate with one another in sharing different experiences and opinions.

Furthermore, the rapid adoption of social media, such as blogs and other social networking sites, as well as media-sharing technology, is altering how businesses respond to consumer needs and desires, as well as how they respond to competitors. This is for a fact since business entities now address issues and concerns of the customers through social media postings as well. Most of the announcements of business firms are now online – through social media platforms.

Additionally, social media represents marketing opportunities that can connect businesses directly with their customers. This statement is factual since we can observe that business firms can now connect with their customers easier and faster through the use of social media. In just a click, advertisements and announcements can be posted reaching millions of people. In the Social Media Marketing Report of 2011, ninety percent

of marketers indicated that social media was important to their business; all these sources only shows that as businesses become more globally competitive, marketing strategies must also become more innovative and compelling in order to attract larger pools of customers. Undeniably, modernization and globalization is already happening here in our country. That is why, business firms must adapt to these changes by creating new marketing strategies that could help them survive in this modern era.

A related study conducted by Tajvidi in 2017 investigated the impact of social media on business performance. The survey was carried out on MSMEs in the hotel industry in the United Kingdom. The study discovered the impact of social media on the performance of MSMEs in the United Kingdom, as well as the potential of marketing to mediate the relationship between social media and firm performance.

On the other hand, the study of Wang in 2017 investigated the role of social media marketing in improving customer relationships and firm performance. According to the findings of their study, the use of social media moderates the association between customer relationship capabilities and company performance. All these literatures are the basis for this study – that is to assess the effectiveness of social media, specifically Facebook as a marketing platform for MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte. Other researchers such as those of Suariedewi in 2022 investigated the usage of social media by MSMEs for marketing in India, and their findings revealed that views of ease of use, perceived convenience, and compatibility all had a major impact on social media marketing. The study of Pires in 2022 evaluated the effect of social media marketing in value co-creation and engagement among Chinese and Hong Kong smartphone users. According to the findings of their study, social media marketing is quite effective in increasing value co-creation, engagement, repurchase intention, and brand awareness.

Essentially, there are also lots of researches being done even before the COVID-19 pandemic. Some related researches are: Effectiveness of Facebook as a free marketing tool, by Palma in 2016. The Implications of Facebook Marketing for Organizations by Ramsaran-Fowder in 2013, A Study on Effectiveness of Facebook Marketing among Economic Students by Avilala Sai Gowtham Reddy in 2019, and others. Technically, all these researchers talked about marketing. Much emphasis were layed on social media marketing particularly Facebook. All those researches were done before the emergence of pandemic, and they all have something in common which is the emphasis of the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform. All those studies attempted to understand the efficiency of Facebook Marketing and how it is the most popular source of social media marketing for businesses those days and even until now.

On the other hand, there has been lot of researches on the use of social media as a marketing tool, but no one has done it during this pandemic. For this study, the researchers aim to assess the effectiveness of Facebook for MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte particularly in this time of pandemic. Accordingly, the main gap for this research study is on the proliferation COVID-19 pandemic. Because of this, many nations have taken serious measures. Many economic actors, especially MSMEs and start-up businesses have been taken aback by lockdowns and limitations on most community activities and economic activity as per Putri, S. E., 2021. With regards to this, the International Labor

Organization (ILO) (Organization, 2020, p. 3; ILO, 2020) performed a survey to assess the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on 571 micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. As a result, 58% of MSMEs reported that they had reduced production of goods and services due to a decline in demand. This survey result is already a problem because business operations were halted due to the pandemic, which will have a significant impact on the enterprise and the economy as well.

As Prenaj and Burim's study in 2016 highlighted the additional benefits of social media marketing – the result was an increase in sales for MSMEs, and also according to the study of Rasheed, Ahmed & Nafiz, Abdulla in 2022, their study concluded that the adoption of social media marketing has a significant positive impact on MSME performance. And this is what the authors of this research paper are trying to prove. Going back to the research locale of this study which is in Abuyog, Leyte, the main gap identified for MSMEs, particularly micro enterprises, is a lack of strategies on how to develop a marketing strategy that will promote and help their businesses earn more, especially in this time of pandemic. And, as technology advanced and the use of social networking sites became more popular, there needed to be a way to make use of these resources to promote and earn a sustainable profit – that is through Facebook marketing. Since using Facebook is the most popular in Abuyog, Leyte, creating Facebook pages for businesses is an excellent idea for MSMEs. With this, the ultimate goal is to evaluate if using Facebook as a marketing platform is effective or not.

Accordingly for this study, the researchers will assess if the status of sales and income, the perceived usefulness of Facebook marketing, and the extent of satisfaction of business owners using Facebook marketing has something to do with the overall effectiveness of the said platform.

Research Questions

This study determined the effectiveness of Facebook as a marketing platform for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Abuyog, Leyte.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of effectiveness of online marketing via Facebook?
 2. What is the status of sales and income of MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte?
 3. What is the extent of usefulness of Facebook marketing platform perceived by business owners?
 4. What is the extent of satisfaction of the business owners utilizing Facebook as a marketing strategy?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the status of sales and income of MSMEs to the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived usefulness of Facebook marketing platform to the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of satisfaction among business owners utilizing Facebook marketing to the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform?
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METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The research on “Assessment on the Effectiveness of Facebook as a Marketing Platform in Abuyog, Leyte” is centered around Abuyog, Leyte. A first-class municipality in the province of Leyte with numerous MSMEs. Abuyog, Leyte is the specific locale of this study, focusing on the marketing aspect of MSMEs in the said town. The goal is to know how effective is Facebook as a marketing platform, and how it helps in sales generation for businesses.

Sampling

The method to be used for sample selection is convenience sampling. The researchers are targeting at least thirty (30) participants and they will be selected based on availability and willingness to take part.

Data Gathering Procedure and Instrument

In this research, a carefully designed questionnaire, underwent validation and reliability test to ensure the quality of the survey questionnaire. The target population, Abuyog, Leyte’s entrepreneurs were selected using convenience sampling. Participants are the selected entrepreneurs utilizing Facebook marketing platform.

For the data collection, the researchers will utilize these tools for data collection procedure: (1) Online questionnaires through Google Forms; and (2) Online interview through Google Meet and/or Messenger.

In checking the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire, the researchers asked the assistance of a statistician in validating the questionnaire and at the same time in computing for the reliability test.

Research Instrument Validation

Category	Rating				Score
	4	3	2	1	
Purpose	Purpose is stated clearly.	Purpose is stated somewhat clearly.	Purpose is stated vaguely.	Purpose is not stated.	3
Clarity of Questions	Questions are very clear. The reader will not have to ask for clarification.	Questions are clear, and a person might have to ask for clarification.	Questions are somewhat clear, and a person would have to ask for clarification.	Questions are confusing and ambiguous.	3
Content	All essential questions	Most of the essential	Some of the essential	One or fewer	2

	are properly addressed.	questions are properly addressed.	questions are properly addressed.	essential questions are properly addressed.	
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Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.951	.964	6

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Cronbach alpha shows that the survey questionnaire has an excellent reliability since alpha is greater than .9. The questionnaire could now be considered as reliable.

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
VAR00001	4.5333	.68145	30
VAR00002	4.5667	.62606	30
VAR00003	4.3667	.71840	30
VAR00004	4.3667	1.09807	30
VAR00005	4.4000	1.10172	30
VAR00006	4.0667	1.22990	30

Process of Analysis and Statistical Treatment

The study's data treatment was rigorous, starting with self-made questionnaire undergoing expert validation and a pilot test. Using convenience sampling, a representative of 30 entrepreneurs using Facebook as a marketing platform was selected, with participants contacted for clarity and confidentiality. Data entry followed a systematic approach, and rigorous reliability and validity testing included the Pearson correlation coefficient. The analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics, with findings presented using data visualization techniques. Throughout, ethical considerations were prioritized, ensuring informed consent and participant confidentiality.

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
VAR00001	21.7667	19.771	.873	.940	.944
VAR00002	21.7333	20.202	.877	.941	.946
VAR00003	21.9333	19.926	.793	.673	.950
VAR00004	21.9333	15.926	.958	.980	.928
VAR00005	21.9000	15.955	.950	.978	.930
VAR00006	22.2333	15.633	.862	.796	.947

Scope and Limitations

The study “Assessment on the effectiveness of Facebook as a marketing platform in Abuyog, Leyte” focused on discovering how effectiveness is the use of social media, especially Facebook as a marketing tool in the time of pandemic. However, in this study, this only focus on one town in the province of Leyte, and only those entrepreneurs who are willing to take part in the study were interviewed and were asked to answer the survey questionnaire.

RESULTS

Shown below are the graphical presentations of the respondents’ answers to the online survey questions through Google Forms.

The data shows that majority of the respondents were from the micro enterprises. Indeed, in Abuyog, Leyte, the researchers directly observed that majority of the enterprises are micro businesses having less than P50,000 as their capital. Majority of these micro enterprises in Abuyog, Leyte are on the food industry.

Figure 1: Summarized results on the survey question “How do you categorize your business in terms of capitalization?”

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Figure 2: Summarized results on the survey question, “How do you categorize your business in terms of employment size?”

Figure 3: Summarized results on the survey question, “Years of business operation?”

Figure 4: Summarized results on the survey question, “Do you have a Facebook Page for your business or are you using your own Facebook account for online marketing?”

Figure 5: Summarized results on the survey question, “Does the use of Facebook as a marketing platform enhances customer relationship?”

Figure 6: Summarized results on the survey question, “Were you able to attract more customers through the use of Facebook marketing?”

Figure 7: Summarized results on the survey question, “How about your sales? Was there a drastic increase in sales when you adapt the use of Facebook for promotion?”

Figure 8: Summarized results on the survey question, “During the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic, were you able to generate more income through the use of Facebook marketing platform? Kindly rate.”

Figure 9: Summarized results on the survey question, “Kindly rate the usefulness of Facebook marketing platform.”

Figure 10: Summarized results on the survey question, “Kindly rate your level/extent of satisfaction in using Facebook marketing platform.”

Figure 11: Summarized results on the survey question, “Kindly rate the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform.”

Results on the Statistical Treatment of Data Using Spss

	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing	4.37	1.098	VERY LARGE EXTENT

1. What is the extent of effectiveness of online marketing via Facebook?

	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
status of sales/income of MSMEs	4.32	1.080	VERY LARGE EXTENT

2. What is the status of sales and income of MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte?

	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
extent of usefulness of Facebook marketing	4.37	1.098	VERY LARGE EXTENT

3. What is the extent of usefulness of Facebook marketing platform perceived by business owners?

	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
extent of satisfaction of business owners utilizing Facebook marketing strategy	4.40	1.101	VERY LARGE EXTENT

4. What is the extent of satisfaction of the business owners utilizing Facebook as a marketing strategy?

	PARAMETERS
(4.21 - 5.00)	VERY LARGE EXTENT
(3.41 - 4.20)	LARGE EXTENT
(2.61 - 3.40)	AVERAGE EXTENT
(1.81 - 2.60)	SMALL EXTENT
(1.00 - 1.80)	VERY SMALL EXTENT

5. Is there a significant relationship between the status of sales and income of MSMEs to the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived usefulness of Facebook marketing platform to the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of satisfaction among business owners utilizing Facebook marketing to the effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform?

	Variables	r value	Strength	p-value	Sig
EFFECTIVENESS OF FACEBOOK MARKETING PLATFORM	STATUS OF SALES AND INCOME	.875	STRONG	$p = 0.000 < 0.05$	S
	PERCEIVED USEFULNESS	.845	STRONG	$p = 0.000 < 0.05$	S
	EXTENT OF SATISFACTION OF BUSINESS OWNERS	.855	STRONG	$p = 0.000 < 0.05$	S

Based from the correlation table above we can say that, “***there was a significant relationship between the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and extent of satisfaction to the extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform.***”

The statistical treatment used is Pearson-r correlation. The tables above shows the correlation coefficient and the p-value. The strength of the relationship can be determined by the value of the correlation coefficient presented as r. The significance level is at .05. So if the p-value is less than or equal the significance level then we consider the relationship significant.

If r is positive that means as one variable increases the other also increases. But if r is negative that means that as one variable increases the other decreases.

Value of r	Strength of relationship
-1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5	Strong
-0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5	Moderate
-0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3	Weak
-0.1 to 0.1	None or very weak

DISCUSSION

Analysis to Every Result

I. Descriptive Analysis

The extent of effectiveness of Facebook as a marketing platform has a mean of 4.37 and standard deviation of 1.098. This means that the result is a very large extent.

The status of sales and income of MSMEs has a mean of 4.32 and standard deviation of 1.080. This means that the result is a very large extent.

The extent of usefulness of Facebook as a marketing platform has a mean of 4.37 and standard deviation of 1.098. This means that the result is a very large extent.

The extent of satisfaction of business owners utilizing Facebook marketing platform during this time of pandemic has a mean of 4.40 and standard deviation of 1.101. This result is a very large extent.

The significant relationship between between the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and extent of satisfaction (independent variables) to the extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform (dependent variable) has been computed using the Pearson-r correlation. After gathering respondent's answers and after computation, the r value for the status of sales and income is .875, the r value for the perceived usefulness of owners utilizing Facebook marketing is .845, and the r value for the extent of satisfaction among business owners is .855. With that correlation coefficient (r value), it follows that the strength of the relationship is strong.

II. Diagnostic Analysis

Based on the respondent's answers, most of them uses Facebook as their marketing platform, thus, it only shows that for them, Facebook is a useful and effective social media marketing platform.

Based on the results of the statistical tool used which is the Pearson-r correlation, the result of the study is, "there was a significant relationship between the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and extent of satisfaction to the extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform." The result is valid since all these are taken from the answers of the respondents to the survey questionnaire.

III. Predictive Analysis

The researchers claim that in the near future, more and more enterprises in Abuyog, Leyte will adapt the use of Facebook marketing platform since they will be able to observe that it has a good impact to the overall performance of the business firm.

IV. Prescriptive Analysis

Based on the results of the study, it would be better if all MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte will adapt the use of Facebook pages as their platform. In that way, their business will be known and it will be easier for customers to contact them since they are visible on social media. The same goes with the placing of orders, it would be more convenient for the customers and the enterprise as well. This can contribute to sales growth of MSMEs. If this happens, all business owners/ entrepreneurs will be satisfied with the use of Facebook marketing platform, and this has an impact to the effectiveness of the said platform.

Conclusions

The purpose of this research was to assess the effectiveness of Facebook as a Marketing Platform for MSMEs in Abuyog, Leyte. This research come into place because of COVID-19 pandemic. Lockdowns and stay at home protocols made it difficult for business enterprises to sustain their sales since customers can no longer go out to shop for their wants and needs. Because of this, the researchers thought that this is really a problem for business owners since their business operations – most especially their sales and income would be greatly much affected. Hence, the researchers pursue this research study in order to assess if using Facebook as a marketing platform is effective enough to reach and persuade more customers amidst pandemic. At the same time, the researchers are eager to find out if the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and business owners' satisfaction towards the use of Facebook marketing has something to do with the platform's effectiveness. This is indeed the ultimate goal for this study.

Based on the analysis conveyed, it can be concluded that **“there was a significant relationship between the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and extent of satisfaction to the extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform.”** This analysis was derived from the statistical tool used in computing and analyzing the data provided by the respondents – through using Pearson-r correlation, through this, the researchers were able to test the correlation of the variables under study.

The result was that the p-value was less than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, there is a significant difference. On the other hand, looking at the r-value of the sales and income, perceived usefulness and satisfaction of using Facebook marketing platform, the digits are 0.875, 0.845, and 0.855 respectively. This follows that the strength of the relationship is strong. Since the r value is a positive number, this means that as one variable increases, the other also increases – meaning there is a significant relationship between the status of sales and income, perceived usefulness, and extent of satisfaction to the extent of effectiveness of Facebook marketing platform.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study "Assessment on the Effectiveness of Facebook as a Marketing Platform in Abuyog, Leyte," it is highly recommended that entrepreneurs in Abuyog, Leyte utilize Facebook as a marketing platform. The study demonstrated a significant relationship between sales and income, perceived usefulness, and the extent of satisfaction with the effectiveness of Facebook marketing. The use of Facebook for marketing purposes has led to increased sales, expanded reach among potential customers, and higher income for entrepreneurs. Therefore, leveraging Facebook as a marketing tool can be highly beneficial for businesses in this town.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the authors of the study titled "Assessment on the Effectiveness of Facebook as a Marketing Platform in Abuyog, Leyte," we affirm our unwavering commitment to maintaining ethical standards throughout our research. We have rigorously obtained explicit informed consent from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time.

To protect the anonymity of respondents, we implemented stringent measures that safeguard their privacy and confidentiality throughout the research process. Our commitment to data protection is in strict compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) of the Philippines. Ensuring participants were shielded from any potential harm during the research was a priority.

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